

20IND11 MetHyInfra

Deliverable D4: Technical report on the inter-comparison of sonic nozzles (CFVNs) of different sizes, shapes, and surface roughness, using alternative fluids (based on e.g. Reynolds number equivalence) with focus on discharge coefficient. The report will also explain their high-pressure calibration behaviour ($p_{\max} = 100$ MPa) and possible differences in their behaviour compared with the ISO curves from ISO 9300

DELIVERABLE D4

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Summary This report was written as part of activity A2.4.4 from the EMPIR Metrology infrastructure for high-pressure gas and liquified hydrogen flows (MetHyInfra) project. The three-year European project commenced on 1st June 2021 and focused on providing metrological infrastructure and traceability for high pressure hydrogen flow meter calibration (1000 bar / 3.6 kg/min), fuel cells applications (4 kg/h, 30 bar) and liquid hydrogen. For more details about this project please visit methyinfra.ptb.de . The purpose of this document is to document an inter-comparison of sonic nozzles (CFVNs) of different sizes, shapes, and surface roughness, using alternative fluids (based on Reynolds number equivalence) with a focus on discharge coefficient (C_d). The report also explains their high-pressure calibration behaviour ($p_{max} = 100$ MPa) and difference in their behaviour compared with the ISO curves from ISO 9300:2022.	
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Contents

1	Introduction.....	4
1.1	Background and context.....	4
1.2	Objectives.....	4
2	Methodology.....	5
2.1	Selection of CFVNs.....	5
2.2	Reynolds number equivalence.....	6
2.3	Alternative fluid selection.....	8
2.3.1	Measurement system and measurement procedure.....	8
2.3.2	Measurement results.....	9
2.3.3	Interpretation of the results.....	11
2.3.4	Discussion.....	12
2.4	Measurement procedure.....	12
2.5	Participants and experimental setup OF Low-pressure Nozzle Intercomparison.....	13
2.5.1	NEL.....	13
2.5.2	Cesame.....	15
2.5.3	METAS.....	16
2.5.4	UL.....	18
2.5.5	Justervesenet (Norwegian Metrology Service).....	19
3	Results of low-pressure intercomparison of sonic nozzles.....	20
3.1	Method of comparison.....	20
3.2	Results of flow measurements.....	21
3.3	Results of dimensional calibration and effect of different sizes, shapes and surface roughness 23	
4	High pressure calibration behavior of CFVN.....	28
4.1	Behavior of CFVN at $p_{max} = 100$ MPa.....	28
4.2	Results of high-pressure flow calibration.....	31
5	Discussion.....	33
5.1	Interpretation of results.....	33
5.1.1	Effect of surface roughness.....	33
5.1.2	Agreement with ISO9300.....	34
6	Conclusion.....	37
7	References.....	38
	Appendices.....	39

1 Introduction

1.1 Background and context

The overall objective of the MetHyInfra project is to establish a metrological infrastructure which will allow the assessment and calibration of flow meters for the measurement of hydrogen flow at high pressures (p_{\max} up to 100 MPa).

The aim of WP2 is to investigate the feasibility of using alternative fluids to perform hydrogen flow meter calibration using CFVNs. There does not exist many flow calibration laboratories which can be operated with hydrogen at industrial flow rates and pressures. This is partly due to the expense of constructing and operating facilities which are safe for use with hydrogen, a highly flammable and combustible gas. If calibration with alternative fluids is found to be transferable, e.g., using air or nitrogen gas, this could simplify calibrations where hydrogen would be used and reduce costs dramatically. It would also potentially allow existing flow calibration laboratories to give reference CFVNs for use with hydrogen, while calibrating them using safer test gases.

1.2 Objectives

The purpose of this report is

- To document an inter-comparison of sonic nozzles (CFVNs) of different sizes, shapes, and surface roughness, using alternative fluids (based on Reynolds number equivalence) with a focus on discharge coefficient (C_d).
- To explain high-pressure calibration behaviour ($p_{\max} = 100$ MPa) of CFVNs and the difference in their behaviour compared with the ISO curves from ISO 9300.

This report has used results and information that was produced in previous reports, from other activities in the work package of the MetHyInfra research project. (MacDonald, 2023) (Bobovnik G. S., 2022).

2 Methodology

The order of the work that was done in the MetHyInfra project is shown in Figure 1. The following subsections in this chapter will detail the work in that figure, but the high-pressure flow measurements are treated in a separate chapter.

Figure 1: The order of work in the project MetHyInfra concerning the CFVNs, and the scope of the various deliverables, including the current document. Note that the arrows do not necessarily indicate the flow of CFVNs.

2.1 Selection of CFVNs

In this project, a selection of different CFVNs were designed and produced. The CFVN were produced with differing parameters, such as diameter, surface roughness, and shape, to assess how they affect the measurement results and their influence on the discharge coefficient.

A total of 14 CFVNs were designed and produced in WP1. Of these 14, 12 were intended for the low-pressure (LP) measurements, while 2 were intended for the high-pressure (HP) measurements. A summary is shown in Table 1. All the CFVNs were designed according to ISO9300 (European Committee for Standardization, 2022).

Table 1: Summary of CFVNs used in this report.

Name	Set A	Set B
Intended use	High-pressure measurements	Low-pressure measurements
Number of CFVNs	2	12
Upper flow measurement range	≥ 2 kg/min (at 90 MPa with H ₂) ¹	Up to 2.3 kg/min (at 20 MPa with H ₂) ²
Pressure range	90 MPa	20 MPa
Shape	1 toroidal and 1 cylindrical throat	6 toroidal and 6 cylindrical throat
Surface roughness	Same roughness	3 different roughnesses
Diameters	1 mm	Six with 1 mm and six with 2 mm

The details about the design of the nozzles are available in the technical report that was produced during this project (D. Kleider, 2022).

All the CFVN were first dimensionally calibrated, before being calibrated by the flow standards of the partners. Parameters such as diameter, concentricity, roughness, and profile shape were measured, and a Good Practice Guide was written based on the results (Marc MacDonald, 2022).

2.2 Reynolds number equivalence

When comparing experimental setups, which may differ in pressure ranges or in the fluids that are used, the Reynolds number is a helpful non-dimensional quantity. Additionally, it allows comparison to the target real hydrogen application. In this report, the real hydrogen application is 100 MPa and a mass flow rate ≤ 3.6 kg/min³.

A comparison test between the participating partners was carried out at low-to-medium pressures, calibrating the 12 CFVNs. The purpose was to measure the discharge coefficient, C_d , against the Reynolds number, Re . The flow rates and pressure of the calibration were selected to ensure a Reynolds equivalence to hydrogen, as detailed in a project report A2.1.4.

Due to the difficulties of operating laboratories with hydrogen gas, it is of interest to assess the feasibility of using alternative methods or fluids to perform calibrations. These fluids may be nitrogen gas, compressed air, etc. If it is feasible, this could open up an alternative traceability route for existing laboratories.

To validate the hydrogen equivalence calculations, testing was performed at the real hydrogen application pressures.

The Reynolds number, Re , is defined as

$$Re = \frac{4 q_m}{\pi d \mu}$$

¹ Note that 90 MPa, rather than 100 MPa, is the maximum pressure due to safety issues.

² For reference, the figure corresponds to ≥ 10 kg/min at 100 MPa with H₂.

³ The real hydrogen application in this project is during the refuelling of hydrogen vehicles.

Where q_m is the mass flow rate [kg/s], d is the diameter [m], and μ is the fluid viscosity (dynamic) [Pa s].

The mass flow rate, q_m , through an ideal CFVN is

$$q_{m,i} = \frac{A_{nt} C^{*,i} p_0}{\sqrt{\left(\frac{R}{M}\right) T_0}}$$

Where A_{nt} is the throat area [m²], $C^{*,i}$ is the critical flow function [-], p_0 is the stagnation pressure [Pa], R is the universal gas constant [kJ mol⁻¹ K⁻¹], M is the molar mass [g mol⁻¹], and T_0 is the stagnation temperature [K]. The equation is given in ISO9300 (European Committee for Standardization, 2022).

The measurement range of each partner was calculated in terms of Reynolds number and is shown in Figure 2. As can be seen from the figure, there exists overlap between the laboratories of the partners.

Next, the hydrogen equivalence was calculated at different pressures. This is shown in Figure 3. It was calculated by substituting the fluid properties of hydrogen, at different pressures, and at two CFVN diameters. It shows that equivalence is only given at low pressures. There is a large gap between the measurement range of all partners and the target real hydrogen application.

Figure 2: The available measurement range of each partner, in terms of Reynolds number, and for two CFVN diameters. Please note the gap in the y-axis.

Figure 3: The available measurement range of each partner, in terms of Reynolds number, and for two CFVN diameters, with the calculated target real hydrogen equivalence included. Please note the gap in the y-axis.

2.3 Alternative fluid selection

2.3.1 Measurement system and measurement procedure

Preliminary tests with alternative gases were carried out by UL (Bobovnik, Mikan, Sambol, Maury, & Kutin, 2023). The tests were carried out for three toroidal critical flow venture nozzles with three different throat diameters (d), which are part of a 5-nozzle array (Tetratec) with the inlet manifold diameter of $D = 10$ mm:

- nozzle 1; $d_1 = 0.175$ mm,
- nozzle 2; $d_2 = 0.275$ mm,
- nozzle 3; $d_3 = 0.436$ mm,

where the given diameters d are the values measured by the manufacturer of the nozzles. High pressure cylinders (50 L) were used as a gas source. The pressure regulator (stage 1) was mounted at the outlet of the gas cylinder and was set to approximately 1 MPa. In order to achieve suitable temperature stabilization, the gas passed through a tube coil before reaching the pressure controller (Bronkhorst, EL-PRESS P-502C), which was used to set the inlet absolute pressure of CFVNs in the interval between 200 kPa and 700 kPa. The pressure (Mensor, CGP2500 & CPR2550, $U(k=2) = 0.02\%$ MV or 80 Pa) and the temperature (Tetratec & PicoTechnology; 535T 161 & PT-104, $U(k=2) = 0.2$ °C) of the gas were measured at the inlet manifold of the CFVNs. The piston prover (Sierra Instruments (Bios), Cal=Trak SL-800 & SL-800-44, $U(k=2) = 0.14\%$), which was used as a reference standard, was connected to the outlet of the CFVNs.

All components were connected to the PC with a control program realized in LabVIEW environment. Using the program, it was possible to control the pressure at the CFVNs inlet and save all necessary data for further processing. The reference mass flow rate was determined as the average of ten consecutive readings of the piston prover.

The measurements for each CFVN were carried out at six measurement points; at nominal inlet pressures p_1 equal to (200, 300, 400, 500, 600, 700) kPa. Three repetitions were carried out at each measuring point. The reference mass flow rate is determined as the mean of ten consecutive readings of the piston prover. The results at each measurement point consist of three main parameters:

- $q_{m,ref}$ – reference mass flow rate,
- p_1 – pressure at the inlet of the CFVN,
- T_1 – temperature at the inlet of the CFVN,

Which were used to calculate the discharge coefficients (the discharge coefficient represents the ratio between the actual mass flow rate through the nozzle and the ideal mass flow rate. The uncertainties ($k=2$) of the resulting discharge coefficients were approximately 0.2 % in all cases.

The calibration of the nozzles was carried out with six different gases (the grade of purity of each gas is shown in parentheses: dry air, Ar - argon (5.0), He - helium (5.6), H₂ - hydrogen (5.5), N₂ - nitrogen (5.0), N₂O - nitrous oxide (2.5). All properties of gases were defined using REFPROP v9.0 database.

Special precautions were made for working with hydrogen. First, prior to using the hydrogen the leak-tightness of all connections was tested with helium using a He-sniffer device. During the measurements of hydrogen, the part of the measuring system (CFVNs, the pressure controller and the piston prover) was put under the fume hood as shown in Figure 4. Using the suitable ventilation system, the gas under the fume hood was exhausted into the outdoor environment.

Figure 4: Measuring system with fume hood.

2.3.2 Measurement results

The experimentally obtained values of discharge coefficients for nozzle 1 and 3 and all the gases under consideration together with their approximations are shown in Figure 5 and Figure 6. It can be seen that similar trends (differences between gases) of discharge coefficients are observed for nozzle 1 and

3. This is not the case for nozzle 2 (results not shown), which behaved differently than the other two nozzles and probably cannot be characterized as a standard toroidal nozzle. Besides relatively poor repeatability, also a significant hysteresis was observed during the tests in case of nozzle 2, therefore further comparisons and conclusions are only made for the experimental results obtained for nozzles 1 and 3.

There is a relatively small range of Re where the determined discharge coefficients could be directly compared. However as can be seen in Figure 5 and Figure 6 the values of discharge coefficients of air, nitrogen and hydrogen almost overlap. The results also show that compared to nitrogen (or air or hydrogen) the discharge coefficient for argon and helium is about 0.5 % lower, while it is about 1 % higher for nitrous oxide.

Figure 5: Cd for different gases for nozzle 1 – experiments (symbols) & Cd model (lines).

Figure 6: Cd for different gases for nozzle 3 – experiments (symbols) & Cd model (lines).

2.3.3 Interpretation of the results

Based on the measured values of the discharge coefficients, the gases can be classified into three groups (from lowest to highest values of C_d): (i) helium and argon, (ii) air, nitrogen and hydrogen and (iii) nitrous oxide. The gases belonging to one of these three groups can be characterized by a similar value of isentropic exponent; for helium and argon it is about 1.67, for air, nitrogen and hydrogen about 1.4 and for nitrous oxide its value is about 1.3.

The observed differences in C_d values can be partly explained by comparison of experimental values with the C_d model according to (Ishibashi & Takamoto, 2000), which takes into account the isentropic coefficient:

$$a = 1 - \frac{\kappa + 1}{(2R/d)^2} \left(\frac{1}{96} - \frac{8\kappa + 21}{4608(2R/d)} + \frac{754 + 1971\kappa + 2007}{552960(2R/d)^2} \right) \text{ and}$$

$$b = \frac{4a}{\sqrt{m}} \left(\frac{\kappa + 1}{2} \right)^{\frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{\kappa - 1}} \left(3\sqrt{2} - 2\sqrt{3} + \frac{\kappa - 1}{\sqrt{3}} \right),$$

where

$$m = \sqrt{\frac{2d}{R} \left(\frac{\kappa + 1}{2} \right)^{\frac{3\kappa - 1}{\kappa - 1}}},$$

and $R = 2d$ is the wall curvature of the nozzle throat. The comparison for hydrogen, helium and nitrous oxide is shown in Figure 7 for nozzle 3. It is evident that the difference between measured C_d values for gases from group (i) and group (ii) can be well explained by Ishibashi & Takamoto model. This is in accordance with (Johnson A. , 1998) where the experimental data for hydrogen, nitrogen and argon agreed reasonably well with the Ishibashi&Takamoto model. Also (Tang & Fenn, 1978) found that C_d for nitrogen, hydrogen, argon and helium coincide with their proposed model at $Re > 1000$, which also exhibits dependence of C_d on κ .

On the other hand, the values of C_d for nitrous oxide cannot be explained by the Ishibashi&Takamoto model, which predicts increase of C_d of only about 0.1 % compared to hydrogen. Much larger observed difference in the experimental results could result from relatively low purity (99.5%) of nitrous oxide or the effects of vibrational relaxation; see e.g. (Johnson, Wright, Nakao, Merkle, & Moldover, 2000) for vibrational relaxation effects in CO_2 and SF_6 .

Figure 7: Comparison of C_d for different gases for nozzle 3 (-•- experimental data; --- Ishibashi&Takamoto model [1]).

2.3.4 Discussion

The preliminary study indicates that CFVNs, when used with hydrogen within the tested range of Reynolds numbers in the laminar boundary layer regime, may potentially be calibrated using alternative gases. The preferred options would likely be air or nitrogen, as their discharge coefficient values closely align with those of hydrogen. By ensuring a comparable range of Reynolds numbers during calibration with air or nitrogen as with hydrogen flow, calibration results can be directly extrapolated to hydrogen without requiring additional corrections. Alternatively, another gas such as helium could be used for calibration, as achieving a comparable Reynolds number range is more feasible. However, in such cases, theoretical models would be needed to predict CFVN behaviour with hydrogen. It's worth noting that due to the inaccuracies of the presented theoretical models, this approach would probably lead to increased uncertainty in the final measurements of hydrogen flow rate.

2.4 Measurement procedure

The partners followed a pre-agreed measurement procedure. It is available in a separate report from activity A2.1.4. This details the low-pressure measurements, while the high-pressure measurements are described in the section

High pressure calibration behavior of CFVN.

A leak checking procedure was followed before the calibration was performed. A more precise procedure was then used to check for leaks in greater detail between the test nozzles and the references, where the leakage rate was calculated. Then, a measurement procedure was followed with a focus on keeping a choked nozzle and stability of measurements.

2.5 Participants and experimental setup OF Low-pressure Nozzle Intercomparison

2.5.1 NEL

NEL installed the MetHyInfra nozzle holder in the “low flow line” of their high-pressure gas flow facility, which uses nitrogen evaporated from a liquid source. The nitrogen is supplied to the facility at 12 MPa, this was reduced to the required test pressure (maximum 5.5 Mpa) using a variable pressure regulator. After the device under test and reference flow device, the gas is vented to atmosphere.

An installation diagram is shown in Figure 8. The NEL facility uses critical flow nozzles as the reference flow device, with an estimated measurement uncertainty of $\pm 0.3\%$ ($k=2$) in mass flow rate. Since they operate at lower inlet pressures than the MetHyInfra nozzles, the NEL reference nozzles were installed downstream. The reference nozzles were carefully selected to limit the back-pressure ratio of the MetHyInfra nozzles to 0.3 or less. Since the critical flow nozzles operate at choked flow conditions, flow rates and inlet pressures were controlled using only the upstream pressure regulator, no other flow control valves were required.

Figure 8: NEL installation diagram.

A photo of the installation is shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Picture of the NEL installation.

2.5.2 Cesame

To carry out this work, we used our test bench “M1” which uses dry air under pressure, and it allows to carry out tests under pressure up to 40/50 barg depending on the nozzle used. Furthermore, also significant flow rates can be managed in the test rig at low pressures, i.e., at 1 barg. Flow rates between about 5 Nm³/h and 50000 Nm³/h are possible. Critical flow sonic nozzles, used as a reference, ensure to obtain low uncertainties which are about 0.21% (k=2). The following image shows the “M1” test bench.

Figure 10: Picture of the CESAME’s secondary standard with sonic nozzles (France, Poitiers).

In the frame of this work, the main part of the main part of the bench (mounting) that was used is shown as follows:

Figure 11: Flow metering line at CESAME’s laboratory while performing the CFVN calibration for MethHylnfra.

To calibrate nozzles using CESAME nozzles, we used the following configuration, which involved mounting the nozzle to be calibrated upstream of the standard nozzle.

Figure 12: Illustration of CESAME testing setup.

2.5.3 METAS

Measurements at METAS were performed on a modular test rig (Mobile Normale) that uses master meters traceable to METAS primary standard for gas flow. The particularity of this test rig is that it is primarily used for on-site calibrations and can easily be adapted to suit the requirements of specific calibrations. It consists of an acquisition unit for temperature, pressure and pulses from the reference meter and the device under test. The upstream pressure can be regulated up to 80 bar and the maximum mass flow rate is 2 kg/min for an expanded uncertainty of 0.30 %.

Figure 13 shows the schematic of the measuring setup. The gas source consists of a bundle of high pressure cylinders filled with nitrogen (5.0) up to 300 bar. Various pressure regulators are used depending on the required inlet pressure and flow rate. During expansion from 300 bar to lower pressure, the gas cools down considerably and a plate heat-exchanger (WT) located upstream of the test section brings and stabilises the gas temperature to the required conditions. Temperature is adjustable from $-40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ up to $30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Figure 13: Illustration of METAS test setup.

The CFVN is mounted in the nozzle holder, located between an upstream shut-off valve and a downstream needle valve, the latter allows to set the downstream pressure. Finally, a passive heat exchanger (not shown here) is located before the master meter that measures the volume flow rate at atmospheric conditions. The gas is ejected into the laboratory. The data acquisition unit collects temperature, pressure and pulse readings. It controls also the sequence of measurements (flying start-stop).

The pictures below show the METAS test rig. On the left one can see the heat exchanger, followed by the shut-off valve and finally the nozzle holder. The right picture shows the downstream part of the test rig with the passive heat exchanger and the reference meter.

Figure 14: METAS test rig.

Repeat measurements were also performed with the METAS primary standard (piston prover, shown in Figure 15) for some nozzles. The setup was identical with that of the secondary standard, except that the reference meter was here replaced by the primary standard. The expanded uncertainty of the measurements performed with the piston provers is 0.15% ($k=2$).

Figure 15: METAS primary standard, a piston prover.

The piston prover was operated in a pressure-regulated mode, i.e. the internal pressure in the cylinder chamber was kept constant during the measurements at the level of the barometric ambient pressure prevailing at the start of the measurement (dynamic control of the driving speed of the piston).

A schematic of a typical setup for calibrating CFVN is shown in Figure 16, not shown are the heat exchanger before the nozzle.

Figure 16: Schematic for a typical setup for calibrating CFVN.

2.5.4 UL

UL used the test rig, the installation diagram of which is given in Figure 17. The gas was supplied from gas cylinders (up to four at once). Using a pressure regulator (stage 1) the pressure is reduced to about 2 MPa. The gas then passes through the heat exchanger and before entering the nozzles the pressure (stage 2) is reduced to the required pressure. A reference standard (piston prover) is installed downstream of the nozzle and at the end, the gas is vented to the atmosphere. The absolute pressure downstream of the nozzle was always near the ambient conditions, so the choked flow conditions were always assured. The reference standard and the temperature and pressure sensors (for monitoring the nozzle inlet temperature and inlet and outlet pressures) were connected to the notebook with LabVIEW control program. The latter was also used to record the measurement data. The photo of the test rig is shown in Figure 18.

Figure 17: Installation diagram of UL test rig.

Figure 18: Photo of UL test rig.

The flow tests were carried out up to 13 bar of inlet nozzle absolute pressure and with the volume gas flow rates between 15 l/min and 1500 l/min. The measurement uncertainty ($k = 2$) of the reference standard is equal to 0.45 %. The tests were performed with nitrogen and for nozzles CFVM 9 and 10 (set 3) also with helium and hydrogen.

2.5.5 Justervesenet (Norwegian Metrology Service)

Due to technical issues, Justervesenet could not participate in the intercomparison as planned. Justervesenet is therefore not included in the measurement results.

3 Results of low-pressure intercomparison of sonic nozzles

3.1 Method of comparison

The calibration results are presented in plots of Reynolds number vs. the discharge coefficient determined by calibration. The theoretical discharge coefficient curve determined from the ISO 9300 calculation was also plotted. Close agreement between the calibrated and theoretical C_d implies that the nozzle conforms to the ISO 9300 geometry and vice versa. A plot was generated for each nozzle, containing results from every laboratory, with error bars indicating the measurement uncertainty. This provides a quick visual indication of the agreement between the results from each laboratory.

The formal evaluation of the intercomparison results was performed by calculating the degree of equivalence. The discharge coefficients determined by calibration were compared with those calculated using the ISO 9300 curves. The relative difference in the calibrated and theoretical discharge coefficients was expressed as a percentage error, which was used for the evaluation of measurement equivalence for each laboratory.

The reference value for the intercomparison was determined for each flow rate separately, as a weighted mean error. The weighting is based on the inverse squares of the standard uncertainty for each laboratory:

$$y = \frac{\frac{x_1}{u_{x1}^2} + \frac{x_2}{u_{x2}^2} + \dots + \frac{x_n}{u_{xn}^2}}{\frac{1}{u_{x1}^2} + \frac{1}{u_{x2}^2} + \dots + \frac{1}{u_{xn}^2}}$$

where x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n are errors of the discharge coefficient for one Reynolds number in different independent laboratories 1,2,n

$u_{x1}, u_{x2}, \dots, u_{xn}$ are standard uncertainties of the error in different laboratories 1,2,n including the uncertainty caused by stability of the device. The standard uncertainty of the reference value u_y is given by

$$\frac{1}{u_y^2} = \frac{1}{u_{x1}^2} + \frac{1}{u_{x2}^2} + \dots + \frac{1}{u_{xn}^2}$$

The expanded uncertainty of the reference value $U(y)$ is:

$$U(y) = 2 \cdot u_y$$

The chi-squared test for consistency check was then performed using values of errors in nozzle discharge coefficient at each Reynolds number. The chi-squared value χ_{obs}^2 was calculated by

$$\chi_{obs}^2 = \frac{(x_1 - y)^2}{u_{x1}^2} + \frac{(x_2 - y)^2}{u_{x2}^2} + \dots + \frac{(x_n - y)^2}{u_{xn}^2}$$

The degrees of freedom ν were assigned:

$$\nu = n - 1$$

where n is the number of participating laboratories. The consistency check was deemed to be a pass if:

$$\Pr\{\chi_{\nu}^2 > \chi_{obs}^2\} < 0.05$$

Where Pr is probability. The function **CHIINV (0.05,v)** in MS Excel will be used. The consistency check failed if **CHIINV (0.05,v) < χ_{obs}^2** .

If the consistency check did not fail, then y was accepted as the comparison reference value x_{ref} and U(y) was accepted as the expanded uncertainty of the comparison reference value U(x_{ref}).

If the consistency check failed then the laboratory with the highest value of $\frac{(x_i - y)^2}{u_{xi}^2}$ was excluded for the next round of evaluation and the new reference value y (WME), the new standard uncertainty of the reference value u_y and the chi-squared value χ_{obs}^2 were calculated again without the values of the excluded laboratory. The consistency check was calculated again, too. This procedure was repeated until the consistency check passed.

This enabled the comparison of the mean results of each laboratory to the weighted mean value (REF2), using each laboratory's uncertainty values. The equivalence of the references was quantified by calculating the normalised deviation, or equivalence, in the form of the En value (En2).

$$En2 = \frac{LAB - REF2}{\sqrt{(U_{95}LAB)^2 + (U_{95}DRIFT)^2 - (U_{95}REF2)^2}}$$

where REF2, U95REF2 and U95DRIFT are defined as:

$$U_{95}REF2 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\sum \left(\frac{1}{(U_{95}LAB)^2} \right)}}$$

$$REF2 = \frac{\sum (LAB / (U_{95}LAB)^2)}{\sum (1 / (U_{95}LAB)^2)}$$

$$U_{95}DRIFT = \frac{\Delta \varepsilon}{\sqrt{3}}$$

The ε was calculated as the maximum deviation in discharge coefficient error per Reynolds number at separate calibration dates. To establish equivalence between the different laboratories, the En value must meet the condition of being less than 1. A warning was issued when $1 < En \leq 1.2$. If the En value is greater than 1.2 then the results were considered inconsistent.

3.2 Results of flow measurements

The agreement between the laboratories are tabulated and available in the appendix, as shown in Table 6 to Table 17.

Table 2: Overview of the CFVNs and their equivalence. Equivalence is taken as $|En| < 1.0$, denoted by an “Y”, while an $|En| < 1.2$ is denoted by an “Y*”. The nozzle names indicate their properties. R1 to R3 indicate three different roughness options. D1 or D2 denotes throat diameters of 1 mm or 2 mm, respectively. C or T indicates cylindrical or toroidal geometries, respectively.

Nozzle name	Equivalence NEL	Equivalence METAS	Equivalence Cesame	Equivalence UL
SN01 R1 D1 C	Y	N	Y*	N
SN02 R1 D1 T	Y	Y*	Y	Y*
SN03 R1 D2 C	Y	Y*	Y	Y*
SN04 R1 D2 T	Y	Y*	Y	Y*
SN05 R2 D1 C	Y*	Y	Y*	Y
SN06 R2 D1 T	Y	Y	Y*	Y
SN07 R2 D2 C	Y	Y*	Y	Y*
SN08 R2 D2 T	Y	Y*	Y	Y*
SN09 R3 D1 C	N	Y*	N	Y*
SN10 R3 D1 T	Y*	Y*	Y*	Y*
SN11 R3 D2 C	Y	N	N	N
SN12 R3 D2 T	Y	Y*	Y	Y*

In this section, we present the results obtained following the calibration of the nozzles by the various partner laboratories (NEL, METAS, UL, CESAME) with different fluids.

We will show in the following only the results for 2 nozzles, namely the CFVN03 R1 D2, which is a cylindrical nozzle with a nominal diameter of 2 mm and a roughness of 0.05 μm and CFVN04, a toroidal nozzle with the same diameter and same roughness.

Figure 14 : Cd values comparison between all the laboratories for CFVN 03 (Cylindrical)

The curves that are shown in the previous graph are the discharge coefficients obtained by the different laboratories (UL in violet, CESAME in green, METAS in blue and NEL in yellow, the one in orange is the ISO curve). As it can be seen, the various curves have the same tendency: they increase with the

Reynolds number until they reach their peak at around a value of $Re = 5 \times 10^5$, then decrease with Re . This is a regular trend since the C_d values are increasing from the laminar regime until the transition point ($Re = 5 \times 10^5$ as previously stated), then there is a decrease in the turbulent regime to finally reach a plateau (constant value).

The following graphs show the same curves for the second nozzle mentioned above obtained by the various laboratories:

Figure 15 : C_d values comparison between all the laboratories for CFVN 04 (Toroidal)

The trend and evolution of the discharge coefficient are the same as before. The only change observed is that the value of C_d at any point is greater for this nozzle (toroidal) than for the previous one (cylindrical).

The curves obtained from the calibration of the other 10 nozzles and the En calculations table for the 12 nozzles are in the appendix.

3.3 Results of dimensional calibration and effect of different sizes, shapes and surface roughness

The 14 CFVN were dimensionally calibrated with the Coordinate Measuring Machine (μ -CMM) from METAS. Dimensional measurements of throat diameter, curvature radius and surface structure were performed. Details on the measurement procedure can be taken from the Good practice Guide on dimensional characterization. The analysis of the dimensional measurements was done in two ways:

- by the software of the μ -CMM machine, which outputs directly throat diameter and its associated form error (deviation with respect to the fitted circle) as well as the diameter of the torus that is fitted on the inlet curvature data. The form error is strongly correlated to the uncertainty related to the determination of the throat diameter.
- According to the Good Practice Guide (GPG) using the raw data from the dimensional calibration.

The CMM method locates what it considers to be the smallest diameter by sampling and then samples a circle at this position to determine the throat diameter.

Using the Good Practice Guide, one can use data from the eight surface lines and determine the local diameter of the nozzle along its flow axis (z-axis) and locate the smallest diameter.

The throat diameters of all the nozzles determined using both methods are summarised in the Table 3 below ('C' and 'T' stand for Cylindrical and Toroidal geometry, respectively), the position along the CFVN flow axis (Z-Position, starting from the entrance of the CFVN) is also indicated:

Table 3: Results of measured throat diameters.

Nozzle ID	μ -CMM			Roughness Torus-Fit (nm)	GPG Method	
	Diameter CMM (mm)	Z-Position (mm)	Uncertainty CMM (μ m)		Diameter 8-Point-Fit (mm)	Uncertainty 8-Point-Fit (μ m)
CFVN01 R1 01 C	1.005413	-	1.9	700	1.002727	1.8
CFVN02 R1 01 T	1.01937	1.58963	2.9	800	1.018791	2.9
CFVN03 R1 02 C	2.00313	-	1.1	600	2.001962	3.1
CFVN04 R1 02 T	2.00546	3.17806	2.8	700	2.006107	2.8
CFVN05 R2 01 C	1.01065	-	8.9	700	1.004193	7.8
CFVN06 R2 01 T	1.02115	1.47635	6.0	500	1.023442	6.0
CFVN07 R2 02 C	2.00122	-	1.7	1000	1.999442	3.1
CFVN08 R2 02 T	1.99664	3.07907	2.0	300	1.996534	2.0
CFVN09 R3 01 C	0.99466	-	3.9	600	0.991178	7.3
CFVN10 R3 01 T	0.98812	1.46458	5.8	1000	0.989866	5.8
CFVN11 R3 02 C	1.99700	-	2.7	1000	1.995682	4.2
CFVN12 R3 02 T	1.99021	3.01945	2.7	1300	1.988653	2.7
CFVN13 R1 01 C	1.00502	-	2.3	600	1.003995	1.9
CFVN14 R1 01 T	1.02496	1.58645	3.4	800	1.025148	3.4

As can be seen, there are notable differences between the obtained throat diameters depending on the analysis method, ranging from 0.1 μm to 6.3 μm in the worst case. This could be an indication that the CMM method does not determine the throat diameter at the narrowest part. Dimensional calibration experts suspect that this difference is caused by the form error from the nozzle surface and that this difference is simply a demonstration of the uncertainty of the dimensional calibration.

A typical form error plot is shown in Figure 19, which shows the 601 data points as measured by the CMM at one position along the nozzle axis CFVN03 (2 mm, smooth surface) and the resulting fitted circle in green using all data points. The maximum form error is calculated from the maximum difference between the points with the largest and smallest distance with respect to the circle centre. In this example, this amounts to 2.64 μm

Figure 19: Form error plot for a nozzle with a 'smooth' roughness.

The same form error at the throat but for a 2 mm nozzle with the roughest surface is shown in Figure 20. The maximum form error for this nozzle amounts to 2.38 μm , which is quite similar to the other nozzle with a better surface finish.

Figure 20: Form error plot for a nozzle with the highest roughness.

It is therefore likely that the differences in throat diameter using the CMM method or the Good Practice Guide are the result from form error and which z-position is used.

The resulting expanded uncertainty for the determination of the throat diameter of such small nozzles is in the range (1 to 2) μm due to the irregular surface of the nozzle.

The determination of the radius of curvature of the nozzle allows to determine the transition from the torus to conical or cylindrical part of the nozzle: for a toroidal nozzle, the curvature ratio should be between (0.227 and 0.277) and 0.5 for a cylindrical nozzle, respectively. One should be careful with the interpretation as the data is very noisy.

One example is shown in Figure 21. The left part of the figure shows the surface of the nozzle while the right part shows the calculated curvature along the nozzle axis.

Figure 21: Left: surface of the nozzle. Right: calculated curvature along nozzle axis.

One clearly recognises the inlet curvature of 0.5 and the transition to the cylindrical part at the position $z/n = 100$, which identifies this as a cylindrical nozzle (CFVN03, 2 mm, smooth surface).

The identification is not always as obvious as can be seen in Figure 22, which is the same plot as the figure before but for CFVN12 (2 mm, roughest surface). The transition should start at around $z/n = 200$ and one observes indeed an average curvature between 0.2 and 0.4 until $z/n = 200$, which slowly decreases along the nozzle axis.

Figure 22: Left: surface of the nozzle. Right: calculated curvature along nozzle axis.

Throat diameter and geometry of nozzles can be inferred from the dimensional calibration results. However, the form error of such small nozzles seems to be the limiting factor for the determination of the throat diameter. No clear effect from surface roughness could be observed as it was masked by form error. The dimensional calibration of such small nozzles presents uncertainty limitations. Moreover, we are talking here about a geometrical throat diameter while a wet calibration determines the fluid mechanical throat diameter which corresponds simply to the narrowest point in the nozzle.

4 High pressure calibration behavior of CFVN

The plan for carrying out the high-pressure calibrations is described below. Unfortunately, the measurements could not be performed in time and included in this report. The calibrations were planned for Week 12 (w/c 18th March), but the researcher from NEL was unable to travel due to illness. The calibrations were re-scheduled to Week 14 (w/c 1st April). They will be performed after the publication of this report, and the results will be included as an addendum/update.

4.1 Behavior of CFVN at $p_{\max} = 100$ MPa

Although critical flow nozzles are well established as secondary flow standards, the behaviour at high pressures (up to 100 MPa) is not fully known. Calibrations at 100 MPa are performed in this project to provide new data in the high-pressure range. In addition, the calibrations allow for a validation of the method of using lower-pressure calibrations using alternative fluids, as described in subsection 2.2 and subsection 2.3.

A modified Maximator test facility will be used to circulate hydrogen at the flow rate and pressure ranges required for the nozzle calibration. A schematic of the facility is shown in Figure 23.

Figure 23: Maximator Test Facility sketch.

Two compressors are used to circulate the hydrogen in a closed loop, the compressors can operate with very high differential pressures, as required to maintain choked flow through the critical flow nozzles at high inlet pressures. Pressure control is achieved using regulators. A back-pressure regulator maintains the pressure at the compressor outlet, whilst a pressure reducing regulator at the end of the test line sets the compressor inlet pressure. The reference used for the flow calibration is a Coriolis meter, which has previously been calibrated in a hydrogen refuelling station (HRS) dispenser against the CESAME mobile gravimetric primary standard, see A1.3.4, Deliverable D1.

The Coriolis master meter and critical flow nozzles will be installed near the end of the test line, immediately upstream of the pressure reducing regulator. The presence of two pressure regulators and a critical flow nozzle divides the test facility into four zones operating at different pressures. There are several pressure vessels throughout the test facility, which improve pressure and flow stability and temporarily allow the facility to operate at higher flow rates than the compressors alone can provide. Heat exchangers provide temperature control upstream of devices under test and in the return line to

the compressor. The test facility has its own mass flow meter, whilst this will not be used for reference metering it should allow test conditions to be established more easily than using the master meter.

Two nozzles will be calibrated. Both have a throat diameter of 1 mm, but one has the toroidal-throat geometry according to ISO 9300, and the other has the cylindrical shape. Although they will be calibrated individually, two critical flow nozzles and holders will be installed in the test facility at the same time but isolated when not in use. This allows the number of pressurisation and depressurisation cycles to be minimised.

A drawing of the test installation is shown in Figure 24 and a photo is shown in Figure 25. The flow direction is from left to right. Hydrogen is first introduced to the Coriolis master meter. The flow then splits into two parallel branches, one nozzle holder is installed in each branch, and a pair of manual isolation valves can be used to isolate the gas flow through either branch.

Figure 24: Drawing of the test installation.

Figure 25: Photo of the test installation.

The test line will be installed at the Maximator facility inside a container, this is shown in Figure 26. This is an ATEX zone, so all instruments used in the test line are ATEX certified for use with hydrogen.

The instruments are connected to power supplies and data logging equipment in the non-ATEX area via intrinsically safe barriers.

Figure 26: Test line as installed in the Maximator facility.

Measurements will be logged and analysed with a laptop equipped with LabVIEW software. Figure 27 shows the LabVIEW user interface.

Figure 27: LabVIEW user interface.

4.2 Results of high-pressure flow calibration

The high-pressure flow calibration of the sonic nozzles was unsuccessful in this project. The reason for that was due to the master meter failing to provide accurate reference flow rates, with the most likely reason being a transmitter unit malfunction. An attempt was made to use the process flow meter installed in the test facility as a reference, but while its performance is suitable for its intended purpose, it proved to lack the required uncertainty level to act as a reference meter.

The calibration results of the attempted use with the process meter are shown in Figure 28. There are reasons to suspect that the data is not reliable. More details on the calibration procedure and the issues that arose can be found in the coming Deliverable D2 of the MetHyInfra project.

The lack of reliable high-pressure hydrogen measurement data means that the high-pressure calibration behaviour of CFVNs with hydrogen remains unknown. It also means that it is not possible to compare the behaviour with the ISO curves from ISO9300.

The suggested calibration methodology may still prove feasible for future research. For more details and recommendations for future approaches the details may be found in Deliverable D2 of the MetHyInfra project.

Figure 28: Calibration results using Maximator process meter as reference. Note that there is reason to suspect that the data is unreliable. Figure reproduced from D2.

5 Discussion

5.1 Interpretation of results

In the low-pressure intercomparison, it was found that 9 out of the 12 nozzles were meeting the condition of demonstrating an absolute En value below 1.2, and thus establishing equivalence between the laboratories. 3 out of the 12 nozzles were showing inconsistent results, i.e., an absolute En value of above 1.2. In this intercomparison, no nozzle was able to demonstrate an En value below 1.0 for all of the participants.

The 3 nozzles showing inconsistent results were:

- SN01 R1 D1 C
- SN09 R3 D1 C
- SN11 R3 D2 C

Notably, all of the nozzles demonstrating En values above 1.2 were of the cylindrical geometries. There is otherwise no common factor for all three nozzles, with two of them having 1 mm throat diameters and one of them having 2 mm throat diameter, and two of them having a “high” roughness and one of them having a “smooth” surface.

5.1.1 Effect of surface roughness

Three different surface roughnesses were used. This is shown in the below table.

Table 4: The three surface roughness options for the CFVNs, where Ra indicates arithmetic average roughness. Reproduced from (D. Kleider, 2022).

Option	Roughness	Roughness, Ra
a	Polished	Ra < 0.1 µm
b	Ra/d about 6e-5	0.4 µm < Ra < 0.6 µm
c	Ra/d about 4e-4	0.9 µm < Ra < 1.1 µm

Table 5: Overview of the CFVNs and their surface roughness.

Nozzle number	Roughness option	Toroidal or cylindrical	Nominal diameter [mm]	Nozzle set
SN01	a	C	1	B
SN02	a	T	1	B
SN03	a	C	2	B
SN04	a	T	2	B
SN05	b	C	1	B
SN06	b	T	1	B
SN07	b	C	2	B
SN08	b	T	2	B
SN09	c	C	1	B
SN10	c	T	1	B
SN11	c	C	2	B

SN12	c	T	2	B
SN13	a	C	1	A
SN14	a	T	1	A

5.1.2 Agreement with ISO9300

All of the discharge coefficient measurements in this report are compared to the ISO9300 values. Both the 2005 and 2022 curves are presented for some of the nozzles in this section.

In previous versions of the ISO9300 standard, published in 2005, the equation for determining the discharge coefficient was given by the following formula (called eq. 10, in section 8.2.2 of the standard):

$$C_{d'} = a - b Re_{nt}^{-n}.$$

Where coefficients a , b and n are constants that are tabulated, and are different for toroidal-throat, accurately machined toroidal-throat, and cylindrical-throat Venturi nozzles.

In 2022, the standard was updated, including the discharge coefficient formula. Now, it is given as (eq. 17 in section 10.3.1)

$$C_d = (a - b Re^{-n}) - \frac{(c - d Re^{-n})}{1 + \exp\left(e - \frac{Re}{f}\right)}.$$

Additional coefficients are constants that are tabulated and are different for toroidal-throat and cylindrical throat Venturi nozzles. The new formula is intended to capture the laminar-turbulent transition.

In this intercomparison, the C_d deviation from the 2005 formula is in the range of -2.061% to $+0.4\%$. The 2022 formula, on the other hand, overpredicts the C_d coefficient in the laminar-turbulent transition region jump in almost all the cases. A few examples are shown in Figure 29, Figure 30 and Figure 31.

Figure 29: SN03 R2 D2 C, with two ISO9300 curves.

Figure 30: SN04 R1 D2 T, with two ISO9300 curves.

Figure 31: SN12 R3 D2 T, with two ISO9300 curves.

6 Conclusion

In the low-pressure intercomparison it was found that 9 out of the 12 nozzles were meeting the condition of demonstrating an En value below 1.2, and thus establishing equivalence between the laboratories. 3 out of the 12 nozzles were showing inconsistent results. Notably, all of the nozzles showing inconsistent results were of a cylindrical geometry.

High-pressure measurements could not be performed due to a technical malfunction of the master meter. An attempt was made to use a different meter, a process meter that was already installed, but it proved to not be suitable for the calibrations. Thus, the high-pressure nozzle calibration behaviour is not yet known.

A preliminary study does indicate that CFVNs may potentially be calibrated using alternative gases to hydrogen, when used with hydrogen gas within a range of tested Reynolds numbers. This holds for tests within the laminar boundary layer regime, and the options for the alternative gases could be air, nitrogen or, with additional corrections, helium. For a Reynolds numbers range in the transitional or turbulent boundary layer regime, the behaviour is still not known.

7 References

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Appendices

Low-pressure intercomparison results and laboratory agreement

In Table 6 to Table 17, equivalence is taken as $|En| < 1.0$, and is shown with a white cell background, while an $|En| < 1.2$ is shown in a yellow cell background with yellow text, and $|En| > 1.2$ is shown with an orange accent and red text. The nozzle names indicate their properties. R1 to R3 indicate three different roughness options. D1 or D2 denotes throat diameters of 1 mm or 2 mm, respectively. C or T indicate cylindrical or toroidal geometries, respectively.

Table 6: SN01 R1 D1 C.

SN01 R1 D1 C	NEL	METAS	CESAME	UL
Test point (bar)	EN2	EN2	EN2	EN2
3		1,408		-1,408
5		1,073		-1,073
8		1,163		-1,163
13	0,242	1,423	-1,125	-0,444
15		1,129	-1,129	
20	0,208	0,837	-0,902	
30	0,325	0,732	-0,912	
40	0,773		-0,773	
51 - 55	0,917		-0,917	

Table 7: SN02 R1 D1 T.

SN02 R1 D1 T	NEL	METAS	CESAME	UL
Test point (bar)	EN2	EN2	EN2	EN2
3		1,005		-1,005
5		0,721		-0,721
8		0,538		-0,538
13	-0,044	0,697	-0,425	-0,203
15		0,615	-0,615	
20	0,235	0,446	-0,588	
30	0,416	0,286	-0,606	
40	0,761		-0,761	
51 - 55	0,888		-0,888	

Table 8: SN03 R1 D2 C.

SN03 R1 D2 C	NEL	METAS	CESAME	UL
Test point (bar)	EN2	EN2	EN2	EN2
3		1,140		-1,140
5		0,788		-0,788
8		0,713		-0,713
13	-0,007	-0,026	0,611	-0,972
15		-0,299	0,299	
20	0,223	-0,411	0,163	
30	-0,592	-0,041	0,547	
40	-0,538		0,538	
51 - 55	-0,753		0,753	

Table 9: SN04 R1 D2 T.

SN04 R1 D2 T	NEL	METAS	CESAME	UL
Test point (bar)	EN2	EN2	EN2	EN2
3		1,028		-1,028
5		0,645		-0,645
8		0,517		-0,517
13	0,477	0,627	-0,432	-0,818
15		0,554	-0,554	
20	0,581	0,305	-0,765	
30	-0,222	0,533	-0,269	
40	0,221		-0,221	
51 - 55	0,107		-0,107	

Table 10: SN05 R2 D1 C.

SN05 R2 D1 C	NEL	METAS	CESAME	UL
Test point (bar)	EN2	EN2	EN2	EN2
3		0,268		-0,268
5		0,244		-0,244
8		0,012		-0,012
13	0,192	-0,332	0,236	-0,020
15		-0,359	0,359	
20	0,513	-0,374	0,014	
30	0,351		-0,351	
40	0,515		-0,515	
51 - 55	1,053		-1,053	

Table 11: SN06 R2 D1 T.

SN06 R2 D1 T	NEL	METAS	CESAME	UL
Test point (bar)	EN2	EN2	EN2	EN2
3		0,390		-0,390
5		0,330		-0,330
8		0,344		-0,344
13	0,371	0,858	-1,089	-0,292
15		0,984	-0,984	
20	0,032	0,920	-1,029	
30	0,383		-0,383	
40	0,360		-0,360	
51 - 55	0,884		-0,884	

Table 12: SN07 R2 D2 C.

SN07 R2 D2 C	NEL	METAS	CESAME	UL
Test point (bar)	EN2	EN2	EN2	EN2
3		1,108		-1,108
5		0,727		-0,727
8		0,601		-0,601
13	-0,185	1,029	-0,729	
15		0,949	-0,949	
20	0,387	0,437	-0,711	
30	-0,277	0,632	-0,306	
40	0,073		-0,073	
51 - 55	-0,070		0,070	

Table 13: SN08 R2 D2 T.

SN08 R2 D2 T	NEL	METAS	CESAME	UL
Test point (bar)	EN2	EN2	EN2	EN2
3		1,124		-1,124
5		0,772		-0,772
8		0,436		-0,436
13	0,059	0,766	-0,712	
15		0,764	-0,764	
20	0,277	0,562	-0,724	
30	-0,068	0,651	-0,503	
40	0,149		-0,149	
51 - 55	0,009		-0,009	

Table 14: SN09 R3 D1 C.

SN09 R3 D1 C	NEL	METAS	CESAME	UL
Test point (bar)	EN2	EN2	EN2	EN2
3		1,090		-1,090
5		0,673		-0,673
8		0,473		-0,473
13	0,874	0,216	-1,009	0,163
15		0,331	-0,331	
20	1,079	-0,260	-0,706	
30	1,240	-0,355	-0,764	
40	1,308		-1,308	
51 - 55	1,567		-1,567	

Table 15: SN10 R3 D1 T.

SN10 R3 D1 T	NEL	METAS	CESAME	UL
Test point (bar)	EN2	EN2	EN2	EN2
3		1,086		-1,086
5		0,787		-0,787
8		0,516		-0,516
13	0,403	0,478	-0,626	
15		0,835	-0,835	
20	0,400	0,004	-0,349	
30	0,446	-0,140	-0,264	
40	0,960		-0,960	
51 - 55	1,103		-1,103	

Table 16: SN11 R3 D2 C.

SN11 R3 D2 C	NEL	METAS	CESAME	UL
Test point (bar)	EN2	EN2	EN2	EN2
3		1,349		-1,349
5		1,195		-1,195
8		1,187		-1,187
13	0,282	1,628	-1,649	
15		1,479	-1,479	
20	0,566	1,030	-1,378	
30	-0,178	1,181	-0,866	
40	0,237		-0,237	
51 - 55	0,268		-0,268	

Table 17: SN12 R3 D2 T.

SN12 R3 D2 T	NEL	METAS	CESAME	UL
Test point (bar)	EN2	EN2	EN2	EN2
3		1,138		-1,138
5		0,827		-0,827
8		0,372		-0,372
13	0,460	0,652	-0,961	
15		0,795	-0,795	
20	0,640	0,448	-0,939	
30	-0,049	0,672	-0,538	
40	0,262		-0,262	
51 - 55	0,010		-0,010	

Low-pressure intercomparison results

Figure 32: Cd values comparison between all the laboratories for CFVN 01 (Cylindrical)

Figure 33: Cd values comparison between all the laboratories for CFVN 02 (Toroidal)

Figure 34: Cd values comparison between all the laboratories for CFVN 05 (Cylindrical)

Figure 35: Cd values comparison between all the laboratories for CFVN 06 (Toroidal)

Figure 36: Cd values comparison between all the laboratories for CFVN 07 (Cylindrical)

Figure 37: Cd values comparison between all the laboratories for CFVN 08 (Toroidal)

Figure 38: Cd values comparison between all the laboratories for CFVN 09 (Cylindrical)

Figure 39: Cd values comparison between all the laboratories for CFVN 10 (Toroidal)

Figure 40: Cd values comparison between all the laboratories for CFVN 11 (Cylindrical)

Figure 41: Cd values comparison between all the laboratories for CFVN 12 (Toroidal)